

Black body cavity apparatus for measuring the emissivity of Nickel-Titanium based shape memory alloys

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Abstract

Nickel-Titanium based shape memory alloys (SMAs) have various applications in biomedical, actuators, aerospace technologies, and elastocaloric devices, because of their shape memory and super elastic effects.¹ These effects are induced in SMAs by a reversible phase transformation from martensite to austenite. This phase transformation can be achieved by applying stress or heating and cooling. It is extremely difficult to measure the temperature of the NiTi elements with contact thermometers without disturbing the phase transformation parameters. To enable the determination of temperature distribution in NiTi components with infrared thermography, a newly constructed apparatus is presented to measure the emissivity of NiTi SMAs. For this purpose, a state-of-the-art infrared camera (type: ImageIR 8380, InfraTec GmbH, Germany) was employed to analyze the emissivity behavior during the phase transformation. The

emissivity of the SMA was systematically studied by comparing it with a reference-quality black body cavity (BBC) having emissivity better than 0.9995. The calibration measurements reveal that the maximum deviation of the BBC temperature measured with the infrared camera was only 0.15% from the temperature measured with the contact thermometers. The apparatus was also validated by measuring the emissivity of a polished aluminum sample and the obtained results were in a good agreement with the literature data at high temperatures. Finally, the emissivity of two rough and one polished NiTi samples was measured covering the temperature range from 313 K to 422 K with a experimental uncertainty of about 0.01. The emissivity of NiTi varies between 0.1 and 0.28. In the martensite phase, it increases rapidly with the increase in temperature, while decreases slowly in the austenite phase. Moreover, it is investigated that the emissivity of NiTi depends on the microstructure, and surface roughness of the samples.

Keywords: Emissivity, black body cavity, infrared thermography, aluminum, NiTi shape memory alloys.

Introduction

Nickel-Titanium (NiTi) based smart materials are important because of their shape memory effect and superelasticity. These properties are induced in the NiTi shape memory alloys by reversible phase transformation from martensite to austenite, which can be triggered by stress or temperature difference. Because of these unique features, currently, the utilization of shape memory alloys has expanded to cutting-edge engineering applications.² Therein, the shape memory effect is commonly used in actuators and deployable structures, while superelasticity has wide applications in medical stents and elastocaloric devices.^{3,4}

Measuring the temperature of shape memory alloys during operation is extremely challenging with contact thermometers because they can disturb the phase transformation parameters of these alloys. An alternative is using contactless infrared thermography, for which accurate

emissivity data are needed. Currently, the literature reveals an insufficient data situation for NiTi shape memory alloys.

Infrared emissivity is a physical parameter that describes the behavior in which an object emits thermal infrared electromagnetic radiations. It is simply defined as a ratio of the radiation energy emitted by an object to the radiation energy emitted by an ideal black body at the same temperature, geometrical, and spectral conditions. There are numerous technological and scientific applications where accurate knowledge of this physical parameter is needed, such as temperature measurement with pyrometers, radiation heat transfer and heat transfer coefficient measurements,^{5,6} optical constant estimation,⁷ heating efficiency,⁸ and photovoltaic applications.⁹

From an experimental point of view, measuring the emissivity is very strenuous, as it depends on the temperature, wavelength of the infrared radiations, and angle of view.¹⁰ Besides that, emissivity changes drastically with the surface roughness, presence of oxidation layer and impurities, and grain size.^{11,12} Moreover, to measure the emissivity of shiny and transparent materials by comparing them with a black body cavity (BBC), corrections for reflective and transmitted radiations should be implemented.¹³

In the present work, an apparatus was built to measure the emissivity of metals covering the temperature range from 308 K to 423 K. The apparatus has three principal components: (1) a modern cooled detector infrared camera (type: ImageIR 8380, InfraTec GmbH, Germany) with a microscopic lens having 5 μm pixel size. The camera has a measuring accuracy better than 0.5 K and a thermal resolution of 20 mK. (2) A reference quality black body cavity with a cylindrical body and a conical bottom. Its design was based on the research conducted at the National Metrology Institute of Germany (PTB).^{14,15} Optimization of the design and calculation of the effective emissivity of the BBC was performed with the simulation software STEEP, which is based on the Monte-Carlo ray tracking method. It is investigated that the emissivity of the BBC depends on the wavelength of the infrared radiations, angle of the conical bottom, and temperature distribution along the length of the cavity. The present

optimized BBC has an effective emissivity better than 0.9995 for the entire temperature range of the apparatus. (3) An accurate contact thermometry system, with nine Pt100 thermometers, was used for measuring the temperature of the BBC and metallic samples. All thermometers were calibrated according to ITS-90 and had a maximum uncertainty of about 0.1 K.

The temperature of the BBC measured with the infrared camera at emissivity $\epsilon = 1$ has a maximum deviation of only 0.15% from the average temperature measured with the resistance thermometers. After calibrating the camera with the BBC, the emissivity of a polished aluminum sample was measured for validating the apparatus and the results were compared with the literature data. It is investigated that the emissivity of aluminum increases from 0.037 to 0.122 by increasing the temperature from 338 K to 421 K. For temperatures above 350 K, the present data were in a good agreement with the literature data and emissivity model by Lanc et al.¹⁶ However, for temperatures below 350 K, the present data were systematically moving away from the literature data. This is because of the fact that polished aluminum is a highly reflective material with low emissivity and the reflected radiation from the environment becomes dominant in the vicinity of the ambient temperature. Therefore, the reflection correction described in equation (7) should be implemented for accurate emissivity measurements. Whereas, in the literature data these measurements were not implemented.

After validating the apparatus, the emissivity of two rough (S_2 and S_3) and one polished (S_4) NiTi samples was measured covering the temperature range from 313 K to 422 K. The average emissivity of the polished sample $\epsilon_{\text{avg.}} = 0.21$ was comparatively lower than the rough sample $\epsilon_{\text{avg.}} = 0.25$. Moreover, the emissivity of NiTi changes with temperature and surface roughness. In the martensite phase, the emissivity of all samples increases rapidly with the increase in temperature, while in the austenite phase, it decreases slowly with the increase in temperature. This behavior is because of the change in the microstructure with temperature. The present data were also compared with the available literature data by da Silva et al.¹⁷

Their data were confirming the present measurements at low temperatures, however, at high temperatures, their data were systematically moving away from the present measurements by exhibiting a big scatter.

Experiment

Variable temperature black body cavity

The variable temperature black body cavity is a reference quality deep radiation cavity with an aperture. The cross-sectional view of the structure of the cavity is depicted in Figure 1. The cavity is made of copper and has a cylindrical body with an inner diameter of 40 mm and an outer diameter of 60 mm. The total length of the cavity is 263 mm with an aperture diameter of 20 mm. The cavity has a conical bottom with an angle of 75° . Specifications of the black body cavity are listed in Table 1. The inner surface of the cavity is painted with an aeroglaze z306 black paint having an emissivity of about 0.95.¹⁸ Four sample holders were grooved around the aperture of the cavity at its top side. All sample holders were 2 mm deep with 10 mm inner diameter.

The cavity was enveloped with a copper pipe to circulate a heat transfer fluid, which enters the pipe from the bottom and leaves it from the top. For auxiliary electric heating, nickel-chromium resistance wire was warped around the cavity, close to the sample holder, for maintaining a uniform temperature in the cavity. For measuring the temperature of the cavity, nine Pt100 thermometers (type: tmg, WV 82.L-0003) were placed in the wall of the cavity along its length. The maximum uncertainty of these thermometers was below 0.1 K. The black body cavity, copper pipe, and NiCr resistance heating wire were shielded with a 6 mm thick aluminum cylinder. The cavity was thermally insulated with a 40 mm thick armaflex sheet and mounted on a xy-stage (type: OPM-JT250-130) through a teflon stand. The xy-stage has the smallest movement resolution of 0.625 μm and positioning accuracy better than 50 μm .

Figure 1: Cross-sectional view of the variable temperature black body cavity.

Table 1: Specifications of the black body cavity.

tested radiation temperature range	295 K - 423 K
material of construction	copper
inner surface color	aeroglaze z306 black
effective emissivity	> 0.999
inner diameter	40 mm
outer diameter	60 mm
length	263 mm
aperture diameter	20 mm
angle of the conical bottom	75°
maximum temperature difference along the length of the BBC	< 0.5 K
time required for achieving a uniform temperature	1 h
ambient temperature range	294 K - 296 K
mass of the cavity with stand and copper pipe	< 15 kg

Schematics of the apparatus

The schematic of the apparatus with all controlling and measuring devices is presented in Figure 2. For regulating the temperature, a thermostat (type: Huber, Ministat 240) was employed in which silicon oil M20 (dimethyl silicone, CAS No. 63148-62-9) was used as a heat transfer fluid. All Pt100 thermometers were connected through a platinum resistance thermometer (PRT) selector switch (type: ISOTECH-954) to a resistance bridge (type: Anton Paar MKT 50). The thermometers were calibrated according to ITS-90, and validated for the entire temperature range of the apparatus by comparing them with a highly precise Pt25 thermometer (type: Rosemount 162CE) having measuring uncertainty of only 0.01 K. Figure 3 shows the comparison of the nine Pt100 thermometers with the reference Pt25 thermometer (solid line). It is evident that for the entire temperature range, all Pt100 thermometers have a maximum deviation of about 0.1 K from the Pt25 thermometer.

For auxiliary electric heating, the NiCr resistance wire was powered by an electric supply from Rohde & Schwarz type HMP4040. The electric heating was automated with a LabVIEW based PID controller. Ambient temperature and relative humidity of the air can also affect the emissivity measurements. To maintain the ambient temperature at a certain level, the apparatus was placed in an air-conditioned laboratory. The environmental conditions were monitored during the experimentation with a data logger (type: Lufft, OPUS 20) and the respective emissivity corrections were implemented.

Figure 2: Schematic of the black body cavity apparatus with all instrumentation and controlling devices.

For contactless thermography, a modern infrared (IR) camera type: INFRATEC, ImageIR 8380 was employed, which has a measuring accuracy better than 0.5 K and a thermal resolution of 20 mK. The camera was mounted on a z-axis moving stage (type: IP M403.22S) to achieve an autofocus. For analyzing the samples on a microscopic level, the IR camera was equipped with a high performance 3x microscopic lens having a geometric resolution of only 5 μm . IRBIS 3.1 software was used for operating the IR camera and analyzing the thermal images.

Figure 3: Comparison of the nine Pt100 thermometers with an accurate Pt25 thermometer, denoted by a solid zero line. Pt 1 ●, Pt 2 ★, Pt 3 ×, Pt 4 +, Pt 5 ◀, Pt 6 ▶, Pt 7 ▼, Pt 8 ◆, Pt 9 ◆.

Sample preparation

The emissivity of four metallic samples was measured in the present work, namely; polished aluminum, polished NiTi, and two rough NiTi samples. All workpieces were having a disc shape geometry with an outer diameter of 10 mm and a thickness of 2 mm. Details on the surface roughness of the workpieces in terms of arithmetic average surface roughness R_a , root mean square roughness R_q , and maximum peak to valley distance in profile R_z are provided in Table 2. The surface roughness of the samples was measured with a Raman microscope, type: Renishaw inVia Raman microscope RE 04, at ambient condition. Before starting the experimentation, the samples were prepared by cleaning them in an ultrasonic bath at 323 K for 0.5 h by using acetone as a cleaning fluid.

Table 2: Surface roughness of the workpieces used for measuring the emissivity.

sample name	sample label	$R_a / \mu\text{m}$	$R_q / \mu\text{m}$	$R_z / \mu\text{m}$
aluminum polished	S ₁	0.29	0.34	2.59
NiTi rough	S ₂	0.44	0.57	3.93
NiTi rough	S ₃	0.47	0.58	3.70
NiTi polished	S ₄	0.34	0.43	3.30

Emissivity measurement

For measuring the emissivity of metals, the professional thermal image analysis software IRBIS 3.1 was used. As the examined metals in the present work were having a shiny surface, the corrections for the reflection of the environment radiations were implemented too. The emissivity ϵ of a metallic sample is usually derived from a quotient of the emitted radiation from the sample M_S and the radiations emitted by the black body cavity M_{BBC} at that temperature,

$$\epsilon = \frac{M_S(T)}{M_{\text{BBC}}(T, \lambda)}. \quad (1)$$

The radiation intensity of the black body cavity depends on the temperature T and the wavelength λ . It can be computed as spectral exitance $M_{\lambda, \text{BBC}}$ based on Plank's radiation law,

$$M_{\lambda, \text{BBC}}(T, \lambda) = \frac{c_1}{\lambda^5 \left(e^{\left(\frac{c_2}{\lambda T}\right)} - 1 \right)}, \quad (2)$$

where the first radiation constant $c_1 = 3.742 \times 10^{-16} \text{ W m}^2 = 3.742 \times 10^8 \text{ W } \mu\text{m}^4 \text{ m}^{-2}$, and the second radiation constant $c_2 = 1.439 \times 10^4 \text{ } \mu\text{m K}$.

As infrared cameras are not monochromatic devices, they do not evaluate the radiations at a certain discrete wavelength. Instead, each device, depending on its detector type, covers a characteristic interval of the infrared spectrum. Therefore, the obtained radiometric behavior is evaluated within the spectral range of the camera. For obtaining the results, the spectral

exitance is integrated for the wavelength range of the infrared camera,

$$M_{\text{BBC}}(T) = \int_{\lambda_{\min}}^{\lambda_{\max}} M_{\lambda, \text{BBC}}(T, \lambda). \quad (3)$$

An alternative and proven approach for simplification of equation (3) is provided below,¹⁹

$$M_{\text{BBC}}(T) \approx \frac{c_1}{\lambda_{\text{eff}}^5 \left(e^{\left(\frac{c_2}{\lambda T} \right)} - 1 \right)} \Delta\lambda, \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta\lambda = \lambda_{\max} - \lambda_{\min}, \quad (5)$$

where $\lambda_{\text{eff}} = 3.85 \mu\text{m}$ is the effective wavelength and $\Delta\lambda = 3.7 \mu\text{m}$ is the wavelength range of the infrared camera. This approach leads to a reduction in computing effort and meanwhile, emissivity correction can be implemented with precision.

Emissivity correction

Emissivity correction based on equation (1) would lead to the following recalculation of radiation intensity $M_s(T_O)$ of the object with temperature T_O to the radiation intensity $M_{\text{BBC}}(T_O)$ that would be emitted by an ideal black body with identical temperature,

$$\epsilon = \frac{M_s(T_O)}{M_{\text{BBC}}(T_O)}. \quad (6)$$

From an experimental point of view, the application of the above equation is a complicated task. This is because M_s and M_{BBC} depend on the response function of the infrared camera, and also include the background radiation coming from inside the camera. Furthermore, the sample signal M_s does not only include the radiation emitted by the sample, but it also takes into account the environmental radiation reflected at the sample surface, which also depends on the sample emissivity. All these facts make equation (6) experimentally inappropriate for accurate emissivity measurements.²⁰ Pérez-Sáez et al. have compared different methods for

measuring the emissivity and suggested a modification in equation (7) to overcome reflection and background radiation effects.²⁰ Therefore, for emissivity correction, the radiation part resulting from reflection and background radiations was excluded as below,¹⁹

$$\epsilon = \frac{M_S(T_O) - M_{\text{BBC}}(T_U)}{M_{\text{BBC}}(T_O) - M_{\text{BBC}}(T_U)}. \quad (7)$$

It is evident that for performing this correction, a black body temperature equivalent of the reflected ambient temperature T_U is needed.

Experimental uncertainty

The overall expanded uncertainty of the emissivity U_ϵ at a confidence level of 95% ($k = 2$) depends on the standard uncertainties for the temperature measured with the IR camera $u_{T,\text{IR}}$ and with the contact thermometers $u_{T,\text{Pt100}}$, ambient temperature measurement $u_{T,\text{amb.}}$, and relative humidity measurement u_{RH} ,

$$U_w = k \left[\left(\frac{\partial \epsilon}{\partial T_{\text{IR}}} \right)^2 u_{T,\text{IR}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial \epsilon}{\partial T_{\text{Pt100}}} \right)^2 u_{T,\text{Pt100}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial \epsilon}{\partial T_{\text{amb.}}} \right)^2 u_{T,\text{amb.}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial \epsilon}{\partial \text{RH}} \right)^2 u_{\text{RH}}^2 \right]^{1/2}. \quad (8)$$

A detailed uncertainty budget for the emissivity measurement at a typical state point of 398 K is provided in Table 3. It includes the sources of uncertainties and their contribution in the overall uncertainty.

Table 3: Detailed uncertainty budget for measuring the emissivity of the NiTi sample S₂.

source	type	measuring range	standard uncertainty	relative ^a uncertainty
temperature IR camera	ImageIR 8380	233 - 1773 K	0.5 K ^b	2.84%
temperature contact thermometers	Pt100	273 - 523 K	0.1 K	0.57%
ambient temperature	OPUS 20	253 - 323 K	0.3 K	0.46%
ambient relative humidity	OPUS 20	0 - 100 %	2 %	0.15%

^a Relative expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$) value at a typical temperature of $T = 398$ K.

^b Uncertainty of the IR camera for the temperature range of the apparatus.

Results and discussion

The numerical investigation of the effective emissivity of the black body cavity is performed by means of STEEP 3 modeling tool, which is based on a Monte-Carlo ray tracking method.²¹ The simulations were conducted for the temperatures changing from 300 K to 450 K with an increment of 50 K. In the spectral range of the present IR camera (1.5 μm - 5.5 μm), Aeroglaze z306 coating has diffusivity D of 0.82 and emissivity ϵ of 0.95.¹⁴ The effective emissivity of the cylindrical shape black body cavity with a conical bottom depends on the apex angle of the cone. This dependence is demonstrated in Figure 4. This effect can be explained by two different types of reflection, diffuse and specular, inside the cavity. For apex angles between 35° and 75° , mostly the radiations are diffused, while at 90° angle, specular reflections become prominent.²² Therefore, the effective emissivity of the cavity sharply decreases at this point. This particular behavior is also observed at 110° and 150° . Whereas, a uniform temperature black body cavity with a 75° apex angle has an effective emissivity value of 0.999998 at ambient condition.

Figure 4: Numerically investigated effective emissivity of the black body cavity as a function of the apex angle of its conical bottom.

Figure 5 exhibits the effective emissivity of the black body cavity as a function of the wavelength of the infrared camera. In isothermal condition, the BBC has a constant temperature

throughout its body and its effective emissivity remains independent of the wavelength, cf. black pentagons in Figure 5. Contrarily, for a nonuniform temperature distribution across the cavity with a temperature difference of 0.5 K between the top and the bottom of the cavity, the effective emissivity depends on the wavelength of the infrared radiations and the temperature of the cavity, cf. colored triangles in Figure 5. For all non-isothermal temperatures, the effective emissivity is minimum at 1.5 μm and its value increases with the increase in temperature. Moreover, the effective emissivity has the highest dependence on the wavelength at the temperature of 300 K and this dependence decreases with the increase in temperature. For example, at 450 K, the effective emissivity changes from 0.988 to 0.997 depending on the wavelength. Whereas, at 300 K, it changes from 0.973 to 0.994 with the increase in wavelength.

Figure 5: Dependence of effective emissivity of the black body cavity on the wavelength of infrared radiations for isothermal and non-isothermal conditions: isothermal BBC \blacklozenge ; non-isothermal BBC: 300 ± 0.25 K \blacktriangle , 400 ± 0.25 K \blacktriangleright , 450 ± 0.25 K \blacktriangleleft , 500 ± 0.25 K \blacktriangledown .

For the present cavity, it was not possible to achieve the required uniformity in temperature by using thermostat heating alone. This is evident in Figure 6 that at 400 K, there was a temperature difference of about 1.5 K between the top and bottom temperatures of the cavity. To suppress this nonuniform temperature distribution, an auxiliary electrical heater was installed at the top side of the cavity. By utilizing both heat sources at 400 K, the

temperature difference along the cavity was reduced to 0.25 K, which was even less at low temperatures. This temperature difference was below 0.5 K for the entire measurement range of the apparatus. Consequently, the present black body cavity has an effective emissivity better than 0.9995 for the entire temperature range of the apparatus.

Figure 6: Temperature of the BBC measured before and after the electrical heating. Pt 1 ●, Pt 2 ★, Pt 3 ×, Pt 4 +, Pt 5 ◀, Pt 6 ▶, Pt 7 ▼, Pt 8 ◆, Pt 9 ◆. Therein, Pt 1 and Pt2 were installed at the top of the cavity, while Pt7, Pt8, and Pt9 were mounted at the bottom of the cavity.

Figure 7 (a) is presenting the thermal image of the black body cavity captured with the infrared camera at $T_{\text{avg.}} = 398$ K, which is the average temperature of nine Pt100 thermometers. The image is taken at emissivity value $\epsilon = 1$ of the infrared camera. For measuring the temperature, a circle C1 was drawn in the middle of the thermogram with the circumference C_{C1} of 8 mm, denoted by a white color circle in Figure 7 (a). The average temperature of all the pixels inside the circle T_{C1} is 298.4 K. Therein, the minimum and maximum pixel temperatures are 397.6 K and 399 K, respectively. It can be seen that at 298 K, the temperature difference between the contact and contactless thermometers is only 0.4 K.

Figure 7 (b) presents the relative deviation of the temperature of the black body cavity measured with the IR camera at $\epsilon = 1$ to the average temperature measured with Pt100

thermometers. It is evident that for the entire temperature range of the apparatus, the deviation of the temperature measured with the IR camera is below 0.15% than the temperature measured with the contact thermometers. However, this deviation is within the uncertainty of the IR camera.

Figure 7: (a) Thermal image of the black body cavity taken with the infrared camera at $T_{\text{avg.}} = 398$ K. (b) Relative deviation of the temperature of the cavity measured with the IR camera \star to the average temperature measured with the contact thermometers, denoted by the solid zero line.

For validation of the apparatus, the emissivity of the polished aluminum sample (S_1) was measured for the entire temperature range of the apparatus. The arithmetic average surface roughness of the sample was $R_a = 0.29 \mu\text{m}$, measured with a Raman microscope (type: Renishaw inVia Raman microscope RE 04). Emissivity data of the polished aluminum with experimental uncertainties at different temperatures are listed in Table 4. The emissivity was measured covering the temperature range from 338.19 K to 421 K and it varies between 0.037 and 0.128 depending on the temperature.

Table 4: Experimental emissivity of the polished aluminum sample S_1 with uncertainties at different temperatures.

T / K	$\epsilon / -$	$U_\epsilon / -$	T / K	$\epsilon / -$	$U_\epsilon / -$	T / K	$\epsilon / -$	$U_\epsilon / -$
338.19	0.037	0.007	368.37	0.105	0.005	397.51	0.112	0.003

Table 4 : (Continued)

T / K	$\epsilon / -$	$U_\epsilon / -$	T / K	$\epsilon / -$	$U_\epsilon / -$	T / K	$\epsilon / -$	$U_\epsilon / -$
343.54	0.064	0.007	373.34	0.117	0.003	402.89	0.108	0.003
348.58	0.073	0.007	378.15	0.111	0.006	407.57	0.119	0.003
353.15	0.086	0.006	382.87	0.113	0.003	412.31	0.123	0.003
358.53	0.082	0.004	387.77	0.108	0.003	418.21	0.128	0.003
363.49	0.095	0.005	392.70	0.117	0.003	421.00	0.122	0.002

¹ U_ϵ is the expanded uncertainty of the emissivity at a confidence level of 95% ($k = 2$), composed of standard uncertainties of temperature measured with the IR camera $u_{T,\text{IR}} = 0.5$ K, with Pt100 thermometers $u_{T,\text{Pt100}} = 0.1$ K, ambient temperature $u_{T,\text{amb.}} = 0.3$ K, and relative humidity of the air $u_{\text{RH}} = 2\%$.

Figure 8 shows the comparison of the present emissivity of aluminum with the literature data. The emissivity of aluminum is reported by four authors covering the temperature range of the present apparatus. It is evident from all sources that the emissivity of aluminum increases with the increase in temperature, except for the data by Lanc et al.,²³ which are showing a descending trend with temperature. In 2018, Lanc et al.¹⁶ have reported the emissivity of aluminum again with a surface roughness of 1.25 μm and 1.55 μm . In their revised measurements, they reported an increase in the emissivity of aluminum with temperature and showed the dependence of emissivity on surface roughness. Moreover, they developed a mathematical model to calculate the emissivity of aluminum as a function of temperature and surface roughness. Their emissivity model is represented by a black solid line at a surface roughness of $R_a = 1.25$ μm . Their experimental data and the numerical model are in a good agreement with the present data, especially for temperatures above 350 K. However, for temperatures below 350 K, their data are systematically moving away from the present data. This is because of the fact that polished aluminum is a shiny material and has a highly

reflective surface. Because of its low emissivity and high reflectivity, aluminum reflects most of the environmental or surrounding radiations. Therefore, it is vital to implement reflectivity corrections described in equation (7). Whereas, Lanc et al.¹⁶ have calculated the emissivity without reflectivity corrections by implementing equation (6). Masoudi et al. have also reported the emissivity of aluminum and their data are exhibiting a similar trend to the present data with an offset of 0.05. It seems that they have measured the emissivity of a rough aluminum sample compared to the present work but they have not provided information on surface roughness. Moreover, the literature sources Bartl and Baranek and Transmetra GmbH instruction manual confirm the low emissivity values for unoxidized aluminum in the vicinity of ambient temperature.

Figure 8: Comparison of the emissivity of aluminum with the literature data at different temperatures: this work ●, Bartl and Baranek²⁵ ◆, Masoudi et al.²⁴ ×, Lanc et al.¹⁶ $R_a = 1.25 \mu\text{m}$ ■, $R_a = 1.55 \mu\text{m}$ ★, emissivity model —, Lanc et al.²³ ►, Transmetra GmbH instruction manual²⁶ ◀.

After calibrating the apparatus with the black body cavity and validating it with the polished

aluminum sample, the emissivity of two rough (S_2 , S_3) and one polished NiTi (S_3) samples were measured. Unoxidized disc shape samples having a diameter of 10 mm and thickness of 2 mm were used for the experimentation. Details on their surface roughness are provided in Table 2. The magnified images of the rough NiTi sample (S_2) taken with the microscopic infrared camera at $T_{avg.} = 398$ K and with the Raman microscope at ambient condition are exhibited in Figure 9 (a) and (b), respectively. The scratches on the surface of the rough NiTi sample are visible in both images.

The temperature distribution on the NiTi sample is evident at the emissivity value of $\epsilon = 0.256$. The average temperature of all the pixels inside Figure 9 (a) is about 398 K. Therein, the temperature varies between 385 K, (blue color) and 415 K (red color) with a span of 30 K. This is because the emissivity changes from pixel to pixel depending on the microstructure or surface roughness of the sample. The blue color is a low emissivity area and the red color is a high emissivity area, while green and yellow are representing the average emissivity region. For the rough NiTi samples, emissivity was measured in the middle of the sample (green and yellow color area).

Figure 10 (a) shows a microscopic thermal image of the polished NiTi sample (S_4) at $T_{avg.} = 398$ K and at emissivity value $\epsilon = 0.21$. Unlike the rough NiTi sample, a uniform temperature distribution is evident on the sample surface. For a better demonstration of the surface temperature, a horizontal line L1 is drawn in the middle of the thermal image. The length of the line is 0.77 mm and its average temperature is 398.03 K. Fig 10 (b) shows the change in temperature along the length of the line L1 from left to right. The temperature of the line varies between 396.4 K and 399.8 K with a temperature span of 3.4 K, which is about 9 times smaller than for the rough sample. This is because of the fact that the polished sample has a much smoother and uniform surface than the rough sample and the emissivity also remains almost constant for the entire sample surface.

Figure 9: Microscopic image of the rough NiTi sample S_2 taken (a) with the IR camera at $T_{\text{avg.}} = 398$ K, after emissivity correction $\epsilon = 0.256$, (b) and with the Raman microscope at ambient temperature.

For inquiring about the dependence of the emissivity of NiTi samples on temperature, they were heated from the ambient temperature to 423 K with an interval of 5 K. After that they were cooled down to the ambient temperature with the same interval, except for the polished NiTi sample S_4 because the sample was oxidized after heating. The emissivity data for the rough and the polished NiTi samples along with experimental uncertainties are listed in Tables 5 and 6, respectively. For the rough NiTi samples, emissivity varies between 0.1 and 0.289 depending on the temperature. Whereas, the polished sample has emissivity values between 0.094 and 0.239.

Figure 11 shows the emissivity of the three NiTi samples as a function of temperature measured in the present work and its comparison with the literature data by da Silva et al.¹⁷ For the present measurements, the emissivity of all NiTi samples increases rapidly in the martensite phase. The highest emissivity is at about 338.2 K which is in the vicinity of the phase changing temperature of the NiTi samples. Contrarily, in the austenite phase, the emissivity decreases slowly with the increase in temperature up to 422.5 K. The phase changing temperature is represented with a black vertical solid line. We hypothesized that this particular behavior is due to different arrangements of the atoms in the austenite and martensite phases. The austenite phase has a body center cubic structure that is stable at

high temperatures, while martensite has a monoclinic crystal structure that persists at low temperatures. A similar behavior was observed in all three NiTi samples by changing their temperature. Moreover, NiTi has a shiny and highly reflective surface similar to aluminum, therefore low emissivity values near the atmospheric temperature could be due to the implementation of the reflection correction according to equation (7). However, the reflection of environmental radiations could not be avoided in the current experimental setup, only its correction could be implemented.

Figure 10: (a) Microscopic image of the polished NiTi sample taken with the IR camera at $T_{avg.} = 398$ K, after emissivity correction $\epsilon = 0.21$. (b) Temperature distribution along the length of line L1, a white solid line in the middle of the thermal image.

As described before, the emissivity of the rough NiTi samples varies depending on the surface roughness and microstructures on the sample surface, i.e., cf. Figure 9 (a) low (blue) and high (red) emissivity areas. Based on the surface roughness or different patterns of the microstructures, the emissivity of the rough NiTi samples (S_1 and S_2) varies between the two dashed lines (green and purple) in Figure 11. It is evident that the effect of microstructures is high at low temperatures, e.g., at 330 K the difference in emissivity between low and high emissivity areas is 0.3, while at 420 K the difference is about 0.13. It can be concluded that nonuniform surface roughness has a larger effect on the emissivity at low temperatures than the high temperatures.

The present emissivity measurements were also compared with experimental literature data

by da Silva et al.¹⁷ They have reported the emissivity of a NiTi sample between 298 K and 373 K under a vacuum condition. Their investigated sample has an arithmetic average surface roughness R_a of 0.76 μm , which is higher than the present work. However, this was the only experimental data available in the literature showing the behavior of emissivity with temperature. Data by da Silva et al. are confirming the present measurements at low temperatures, but at high temperatures, their data are following a different trend and show a big scatter, while the present data are looking more systematic.

Figure 11: Emissivity of NiTi as a function of temperature. This work: heating rough sample S_2 \blacktriangle , cooling rough sample S_2 \blacktriangledown , heating rough sample S_3 \blacklozenge , cooling rough sample S_3 \blacklozenge ; heating polished sample S_4 \bullet , da Silva et al.¹⁷ heating $+$, cooling $+$, minimum emissivity for samples S_2 and S_3 $---$, maximum emissivity for samples S_2 and S_3 $---$

Table 5: Experimental emissivity of two rough NiTi samples S₂ and S₃ with uncertainties at different temperatures.

heating of samples					cooling of samples				
T/K	ϵ S ₂ /-	U_ϵ S ₂ /-	ϵ S ₃ /-	U_ϵ S ₃ /-	T/K	ϵ S ₂ /-	U_ϵ S ₂ /-	ϵ S ₃ /-	U_ϵ S ₃ /-
313.259	0.100	0.022	0.116	0.022	418.691	0.246	0.005	0.229	0.005
318.249	0.177	0.017	0.186	0.017	412.777	0.251	0.006	0.233	0.006
323.224	0.216	0.016	0.227	0.016	408.001	0.255	0.006	0.236	0.006
328.227	0.245	0.014	0.251	0.014	403.227	0.250	0.006	0.233	0.006
333.216	0.264	0.013	0.269	0.013	397.815	0.254	0.006	0.239	0.006
338.192	0.280	0.013	0.289	0.013	393.049	0.260	0.007	0.248	0.007
343.582	0.283	0.012	0.276	0.012	388.024	0.263	0.007	0.251	0.007
349.212	0.268	0.011	0.267	0.011	383.159	0.262	0.007	0.252	0.007
353.657	0.268	0.009	0.266	0.009	378.345	0.260	0.007	0.252	0.007
358.594	0.270	0.009	0.261	0.009	373.414	0.269	0.008	0.258	0.008
363.535	0.264	0.008	0.260	0.008	368.426	0.273	0.008	0.265	0.008
368.496	0.263	0.008	0.263	0.008	363.503	0.274	0.008	0.263	0.008
373.440	0.263	0.008	0.260	0.008	358.552	0.273	0.009	0.271	0.009
378.366	0.263	0.007	0.266	0.007	353.644	0.279	0.009	0.274	0.009
383.185	0.259	0.007	0.259	0.007	348.660	0.282	0.011	0.282	0.011
388.142	0.261	0.007	0.252	0.007	343.561	0.279	0.012	0.277	0.012
392.915	0.254	0.007	0.248	0.007	338.181	0.269	0.013	0.272	0.013
397.878	0.256	0.006	0.249	0.006	333.203	0.268	0.013	0.262	0.013
403.260	0.253	0.006	0.248	0.006	328.220	0.255	0.014	0.264	0.014
408.212	0.255	0.006	0.240	0.006	323.263	0.238	0.016	0.235	0.016
412.971	0.254	0.006	0.243	0.006	318.252	0.197	0.017	0.204	0.017
418.705	0.247	0.005	0.241	0.005	313.265	0.139	0.022	0.144	0.022

Table 5 : (Continued)

heating of samples					cooling of samples				
T/K	$\epsilon \text{ S}_2/-$	$U_\epsilon \text{ S}_2/-$	$\epsilon \text{ S}_3/-$	$U_\epsilon \text{ S}_3/-$	T/K	$\epsilon \text{ S}_2/-$	$U_\epsilon \text{ S}_2/-$	$\epsilon \text{ S}_3/-$	$U_\epsilon \text{ S}_3/-$
422.488	0.236	0.005	0.231	0.005					

¹ U_ϵ is the expanded uncertainty of the emissivity at a confidence level of 95% ($k = 2$), composed of standard uncertainties of temperature measured with the IR camera $u_{T,\text{IR}} = 0.5$ K, with Pt100 thermometers $u_{T,\text{Pt100}} = 0.1$ K, ambient temperature $u_{T,\text{amb.}} = 0.3$ K, and relative humidity of the air $u_{\text{RH}} = 2\%$.

Table 6: Experimental emissivity of a polished NiTi sample S_4 with uncertainties at different temperatures.

T/K	$\epsilon /-$	$U_\epsilon /-$	T/K	$\epsilon /-$	$U_\epsilon /-$	T/K	$\epsilon /-$	$U_\epsilon /-$
318.24	0.094	0.017	358.53	0.230	0.010	397.51	0.210	0.005
323.26	0.147	0.014	363.48	0.229	0.010	402.88	0.216	0.005
328.22	0.178	0.012	368.37	0.225	0.008	407.58	0.205	0.005
333.22	0.196	0.011	373.34	0.225	0.009	412.31	0.201	0.005
338.19	0.220	0.014	378.15	0.230	0.007	418.21	0.194	0.004
343.54	0.228	0.010	382.87	0.218	0.006	422.00	0.196	0.004
348.58	0.233	0.010	387.77	0.225	0.006			
353.15	0.239	0.009	392.70	0.236	0.006			

¹ U_ϵ is the expanded uncertainty of the emissivity at a confidence level of 95% ($k = 2$), composed of standard uncertainties of temperature measured with the IR camera $u_{T,\text{IR}} = 0.5$ K, with Pt100 thermometers $u_{T,\text{Pt100}} = 0.1$ K, ambient temperature $u_{T,\text{amb.}} = 0.3$ K, and relative humidity of the air $u_{\text{RH}} = 2\%$.

Conclusions

The demand for NiTi based smart materials is increasing tremendously because of their shape memory effect and superelasticity. These materials have numerous applications in biomedicine, deployable structures, actuators, and elastocaloric technologies. However, it is very difficult to measure the temperature of NiTi made components by using contact thermometry without disturbing their reversible phase transformation phenomenon from martensite to austenite. On the other hand, accurate emissivity data are needed for their temperature measurements with contactless infrared pyrometers. Generally, the emissivity of a sample is derived from the quotient of the emitted radiations from the sample and the radiations emitted by a black body cavity at the same temperature. The emissivity depends on the temperature, wavelength, viewing angle, surface roughness, presence of oxidation layer, and grain size. Currently, the literature reveals very limited data for the emissivity of NiTi shape memory alloys. Therefore, an apparatus was constructed to measure the emissivity of metals on a microscopic level covering the temperature range from 308 K to 423 K. For this purpose, a reference quality black body cavity was constructed with an effective emissivity better than 0.9995. A state-of-the-art cooled sensors infrared camera (type: ImageIR 8380, InfraTec GmbH, Germany) with a microscopic lens was employed for infrared thermography. The temperature of the black body cavity measured with the IR camera has a maximum deviation of only 0.15% from the temperature measured with the contact thermometers. The apparatus was validated by measuring the emissivity of a polished aluminum sample with an average arithmetic surface roughness R_a of 0.29 μm . The emissivity of aluminum increases from 0.037 to 0.128 with the increase in temperature because its surface morphology changes with temperature. Moreover, the present aluminum data were in a good agreement with the literature data and the emissivity model by Lanc et al.¹⁶ Finally, the emissivity of two rough and one polished NiTi samples was measured with an experimental expanded uncertainty of about 0.01 at a confidence level of 95% ($k = 2$). It was investigated that the average emissivity of the polished sample $\epsilon_{\text{avg.}} = 0.21$ was lower

than the rough samples $\epsilon_{\text{avg.}} = 0.25$. The emissivity of NiTi varies between 0.1 and 0.289 depending on the temperature. In the martensite phase, the emissivity increases sharply with the increase in temperature, while in the austenite phase, it decreases slowly with the increase in temperature. We conjectured that this behavior is due to the change in the microstructure of the samples with temperature. The present data were also compared with the literature data by da Silva et al.¹⁷ Their data were confirming the present measurements at low temperatures, while at high temperatures, their data were moving away from the present measurements and showed a big scatter.

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References

- (1) Patel, S. K.; Behera, B.; Swain, B.; Roshan, R.; Sahoo, D.; Behera, A. A review on NiTi alloys for biomedical applications and their biocompatibility. *Materials Today: Proceedings* **2020**, *33*, 5548–5551.
- (2) Menna, C.; Auricchio, F.; Asprone, D. *Shape Memory Alloy Engineering*; Elsevier, 2015; pp 369–403.
- (3) Wang, Z.; Chen, J.; Kocich, R.; Tardif, S.; Dolbnya, I. P.; Kunčická, L.; Micha, J.-S.; Liogas, K.; Magdysyuk, O. V.; Szurman, I.; Korsunsky, A. Grain structure engineering of NiTi shape memory alloys by intensive plastic deformation. *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* **2022**, *14*, 31396–31410.
- (4) Farber, E.; Zhu, J.-N.; Popovich, A.; Popovich, V. A review of NiTi shape memory alloy

- as a smart material produced by additive manufacturing. *Materials Today: Proceedings* **2020**, *30*, 761–767.
- (5) Lopes, R.; Moura, L. M.; Baillis, D.; Sacadura, J.-F. Directional spectral emittance of a packed bed: correlation between theoretical prediction and experimental data. *J. Heat Transfer* **2001**, *123*, 240–248.
- (6) Freund, S. Local heat transfer coefficients measured with temperature oscillation IR thermography. Ph.D. thesis, Universitätsbibliothek der HSU/UniBwH, 2008.
- (7) Sova, R. M.; Linevsky, M. J.; Thomas, M. E.; Mark, F. F. High-temperature infrared properties of sapphire, AlON, fused silica, yttria, and spinel. *Infrared physics & technology* **1998**, *39*, 251–261.
- (8) Högström, H.; Forssell, G.; Ribbing, C. G. Realization of selective low emittance in both thermal atmospheric windows. *Optical Engineering* **2005**, *44*, 026001–026001.
- (9) Kandeal, A.; Elkadeem, M.; Thakur, A. K.; Abdelaziz, G. B.; Sathyamurthy, R.; Kabeel, A.; Yang, N.; Sharshir, S. W. Infrared thermography-based condition monitoring of solar photovoltaic systems: A mini review of recent advances. *Solar Energy* **2021**, *223*, 33–43.
- (10) Sabuga, W.; Todtenhaupt, R. Effect of roughness on the emissivity of the precious metals silver, gold, palladium, platinum, rhodium, and iridium. *High Temperatures High Pressures(UK)* **2001**, *33*, 261–269.
- (11) Wakabayashi, H.; Makino, T. A new spectrophotometer system for measuring thermal radiation phenomena in a 0.30-11 μm wavelength region. *Measurement Science and Technology* **2001**, *12*, 2113.
- (12) del Campo, L.; Pérez-Sáez, R. B.; Esquisabel, X.; Fernández, I.; Tello, M. J. New exper-

- imental device for infrared spectral directional emissivity measurements in a controlled environment. *Review of scientific instruments* **2006**, 77.
- (13) Dobesch, A.; Poliak, J. IR thermometer with automatic emissivity correction. *Radio-engineering* **2013**, 22, 1301–1306.
- (14) Morozova, S.; Parfentiev, N.; Lisiansky, B.; Sapritsky, V.; Dovgilov, N.; Melenevsky, U.; Gutschwager, B.; Monte, C.; Hollandt, J. Vacuum variable-temperature blackbody VTBB100. *International Journal of Thermophysics* **2008**, 29, 341–351.
- (15) Morozova, S.; Parfentiev, N.; Lisiansky, B.; Melenevsky, U.; Gutschwager, B.; Monte, C.; Hollandt, J. Vacuum variable medium temperature blackbody. *International Journal of Thermophysics* **2010**, 31, 1809–1820.
- (16) Lanc, a. Š. B., Zorana; Zeljković, M.; Živković, A.; Hadžistević, M. Emissivity of aluminium alloy using infrared thermography technique. *Materials and technology* **2018**, 52, 323–327.
- (17) da Silva, T. C.; Sá, M. V. C.; da Silva, E. P.; da Silva, F. C. Emissivity measurements on shape memory alloys. 13th Quantitative Infrared Thermography Conference. 2016; pp 172–179.
- (18) Best, F. A.; Revercomb, H. E.; Knuteson, R. O.; Tobin, D. C.; Ellington, S. D.; Werner, M. W.; Adler, D. P.; Garcia, R. K.; Taylor, J. K.; Ciganovich, N. N.; Smith Sr, W. The geosynchronous imaging Fourier transform spectrometer (GIFTS) on-board blackbody calibration system. *Multispectral and Hyperspectral Remote Sensing Instruments and Applications II*. 2005; pp 77–87.
- (19) InfraTec GmbH - Infrarotsensorik und Messtechnik, InfraTec Instruction Manual, *Radiometric Correction in IRBIS 3.1*; InfraTec GmbH, Dresden, Germany.

- (20) Pérez-Sáez, R. B.; Campo, L. d.; Tello, M. J. Analysis of the accuracy of methods for the direct measurement of emissivity. *International Journal of Thermophysics* **2008**, *29*, 1141–1155.
- (21) Prokhorov, A. V.; Mekhontsev, S. N.; Hanssen, L. M. Monte Carlo modeling of an integrating sphere reflectometer. *Applied optics* **2003**, *42*, 3832–3842.
- (22) Sapritsky, V.; Prokhorov, A. Calculation of the effective emissivities of specular-diffuse cavities by the Monte Carlo method. *Metrologia* **1992**, *29*, 9.
- (23) Lanc, Z.; Zeljković, M.; Štrbac, B.; Živković, A.; Drstvenšek, I.; Hadžistević, M. The determination of the emissivity of aluminum alloy AW 6082 using infrared thermography. *J. Prod. Eng.* **2015**, *18*, 23–26.
- (24) Masoudi, S.; Gholami, M.; Iariche, J. M.; Vafadar, A. Infrared temperature measurement and increasing infrared measurement accuracy in the context of machining process. *Advances in Production Engineering & Management* **2017**, *12*, 353–362.
- (25) Bartl, J.; Baranek, M. Emissivity of aluminium and its importance for radiometric measurement. *Measurement science review* **2004**, *4*, 31–36.
- (26) Transmetra GmbH - Messtechnik mit KnowHow, Transmetra Instruction Manual, *Table of Emissivity of Various Surfaces For Infrared Thermometry*; Transmetra GmbH, Flurlingen, Switzerland.